

SMARANDACHE NEAR-RINGS AND THEIR GENERALIZATIONS

W. B. Vasantha Kandasamy
Department of Mathematics
Indian Institute of Technology, Madras
Chennai - 600 036, India.
E- mail: vasantak@md3.vsnl.net.in

Abstract: In this paper we study the Smarandache semi-near-ring and near-ring, homomorphism, also the Anti-Smarandache semi-near-ring. We obtain some interesting results about them, give many examples, and pose some problems. We also define Smarandache semi-near-ring homomorphism.

Keywords: Near-ring, Semi-near-ring, Smarandache semi-near-ring, Smarandache near-ring, Anti-Smarandache semi-near-ring, Smarandache semi-near-ring homomorphism,

Definition [1 Pilz]: An algebraic system $(N, +, \bullet)$ is called a *near-ring* (or a *right near-ring*) if it satisfies the following three conditions:

- (i) $(N, +)$ is a group (not necessarily abelian).
- (ii) (N, \bullet) is a semigroup.
- (iii) $(n_1 + n_2) \bullet n_3 = n_1 \bullet n_3 + n_2 \bullet n_3$ (right distributive law) for all $n_1, n_2, n_3 \in N$.

Definition [1 Pilz]: An algebraic system $(S, +, \bullet)$ is called a *semi-near-ring* (or *right semi-near-ring*) if it satisfies the following three conditions:

- (i) $(S, +)$ is a semigroup (not necessarily abelian).
- (ii) (S, \bullet) is a semigroup.
- (iii) $(n_1 + n_2) \bullet n_3 = n_1 \bullet n_3 + n_2 \bullet n_3$ for all $n_1, n_2, n_3 \in S$ (right distributive law).

Clearly, every near-ring is a semi-near-ring and not conversely. For more about semi-near-rings please refer [1], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8] and [9].

Definition 1: A non-empty set N is said to be a *Smarandache semi-near-ring* if $(N, +, \bullet)$ is a semi-near-ring having a proper subset A ($A \subset N$) such that A under the same binary operations of N is a near-ring, that is $(A, +, \bullet)$ is a near-ring.

Example 1: Let $Z_{18} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, 17\}$ integers modulo 18 under multiplication. Define two binary operations \times and \bullet on Z_{18} as follows:
 \times is the usual multiplication so that (Z_{18}, \times) is a semigroup;

$a \bullet b = a$ for all $a, b \in Z_{18}$.

Clearly (Z_{18}, \bullet) is a semigroup under \bullet . $(Z_{18}, \times, \bullet)$ is a semi-near-ring. $(Z_{18}, \times, \bullet)$ is a Smarandache semi-near-ring, for take $A = \{1, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17\}$. (A, \times, \bullet) is a near-ring. Hence the claim.

Theorem 2: Not all semi-near-rings are in general Smarandache semi-near-rings.

Proof: By an example.

Let $Z^+ = \{\text{set of positive integers}\}$. Z^+ under $+$ is a semigroup. Define \bullet a binary operation on Z^+ as $a \bullet b = a$ for all $a, b \in Z^+$. Clearly Z^+ under \bullet is a semigroup. Now $(Z^+, +, \bullet)$ is a semi-near-ring which is not a Smarandache semi-near-ring.

Now we give an example of.

Example 2 (of an infinite Smarandache semi-near-ring):

Let $M_{n \times n} = \{(a_{ij}) / a_{ij} \in Z\}$. Define matrix multiplication as an operation on $M_{n \times n}$. $(M_{n \times n}, \times)$ is a semigroup. Define ' \bullet ' on $M_{n \times n}$ as $A \bullet B = A$ for all $A, B \in M_{n \times n}$. Clearly $(M_{n \times n}, \times, \bullet)$ is a Smarandache semi-near-ring, for take the set of all $n \times n$ matrices A such that $|A| \neq 0$. Denote the collection by $A_{n \times n}$. $A_{n \times n} \subset M_{n \times n}$. Clearly $(A_{n \times n}, \times, \bullet)$ is a semi-near-ring.

Example 3:

Let $Z_{24} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 23\}$ be the set of integers modulo 24. Define usual multiplication \times on Z_{24} . (Z_{24}, \times) is a semigroup. Define ' \bullet ' on Z_{24} as $a \bullet b = a$ for all $a, b \in Z_{24}$. Clearly Z_{24} is a semi-near-ring. Now Z_{24} is also a Smarandache semi-near-ring. For take $A = \{1, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23\}$. (A, \times, \bullet) is a near-ring. So, Z_{24} is a Smarandache semi-near-ring.

Motivated by the examples 3 and 4 we propose the following open problem.

Problem 1: Let $Z_n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$ set of integers. $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t}$, where p_1, p_2, \dots, p_t are distinct primes, $t > 1$. Define two binary operations ' \times ' and ' \bullet ' on Z_n . \times is the usual multiplication. Define ' \bullet ' on Z_n as $a \bullet b = a$ for all $a, b \in Z_n$. Let $A = \{1, q_1, \dots, q_r\}$ where q_1, \dots, q_r are all odd primes different from p_1, \dots, p_t and $q_1, \dots, q_r \in Z_n$.

Prove A is a group under \times . Solution to this problem will give the following:

Result: $Z_n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$ is a Smarandache semi-near-ring under \times and \bullet defined as in Examples 1 and 3. Thus we get a class of Smarandache semi-near-rings for every positive composite integer. Now when $t = 1$ different cases arise.

Example 4: $Z_4 = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ is a Smarandache semi-near-ring as (Z_4, \times, \bullet) is a semi-near-ring and $(A = \{1, 3\}, \times, \bullet)$ is a near-ring.

Example 5: $Z_9 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, 8\}$. Now (Z_9, \times, \bullet) is a semi-near-ring. $(A = \{1, 8\}, \times, \bullet)$ is a near-ring so Z_9 is a Smarandache near-ring. Clearly 8 is not a prime number.

Example 6: Let $Z_{25} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, 24\}$. Now $(Z_{25}, \times, \bullet)$ is a semi-near-ring. $(A = \{1, 24\}, \times, \bullet)$ is a near-ring. Thus Z_{25} is a Smarandache semi-near-ring.

Theorem 3: Let $(Z_{p^2}, \times, \bullet)$ be a semi-near-ring. Clearly $(Z_{p^2}, \times, \bullet)$ is a Smarandache semi-near-ring.

Proof: Let $(A = \{1, p^2-1\}, \times, \bullet)$ is a near-ring. Hence $(Z_{p^2}, \times, \bullet)$ is a Smarandache semi-near-ring.

Hence we assume $t > 1$, for non primes one can contribute to near -ring under (\times, \bullet) .

Corollary: Let $(Z_{p^n}, \times, \bullet)$ be a semi-near-ring. $(Z_{p^n}, \times, \bullet)$ is a Smarandache near-ring.

Proof: Take $A = \{1, p^n-1\}$ is a near-ring. Hence $(Z_{p^n}, \times, \bullet)$ is a Smarandache semi-near-ring.

Thus we have a natural class of finite Smarandache semi-near-rings.

Definition 4 (in the classical way):

N is said to be a *Smarandache near-ring* if $(N, +, \bullet)$ is a near-ring and has a proper subset A such that $(A, +, \bullet)$ is a near-field.

Now many near-rings contain subsets that are semi-near-rings, so we are forced to check:

Definition 5: N is said to be an *Anti-Smarandache semi-near-ring* if N is a near-ring and has a proper subset A of N such that A is a semi-near-ring under the same operations of N .

Example 7: Let Z be the set of integers under usual $+$ and multiplication ' \bullet ' by $a \bullet b = a$ for all $a, b \in Z$. $(Z, +, \bullet)$ is a near-ring. Take $A = Z^+$ now $(Z^+, +, \bullet)$ is a semi-near-ring. So Z is an Anti-Smarandache semi-near-ring.

Example 8: Let $M_{n \times n} = \{(a_{ij}) / a_{ij} \in Z\}$. Define $+$ on $M_{n \times n}$ as the usual addition

of matrices and define \bullet on $M_{n \times n}$ by $A \bullet B = A$ for all $A, B \in M_{n \times n}$. $(M_{n \times n}, +, \bullet)$ is a near-ring. Take $A_{n \times n} = \{(a_{ij}) / a_{ij} \in Z^+\}$. Now $(A, +, \bullet)$ is a semi-near-ring. Thus $M_{n \times n}$ is an Anti-Smarandache semi-near-ring.

We propose the following:

Problem 2: Does there exist an infinite near-ring constructed using reals or integers, which is not an Anti-Smarandache semi-near-ring?

Example 9: $Z[x]$ is the polynomial ring over the ring of integers. Define $+$ on $Z[x]$ as the usual addition of polynomials. Define an operation \bullet on $Z[x]$ as $p(x) \bullet q(x) = p(x)$ for all $p(x), q(x) \in Z[x]$. Clearly $(Z[x], +, \bullet)$ is an Anti-Smarandache semi-near-ring, for $(Z^+[x], +, \bullet)$ is a semi-near-ring.

Now it is still more interesting to find a solution to the following question (or Problem 2 worded in a negative way):

Problem 3: Find a finite Anti-Smarandache semi-near-ring.

Definition 6: Let N and N_1 be two Smarandache semi-near-rings. A mapping $h: N \rightarrow N_1$ is a *Smarandache semi-near-ring homomorphism* if h is a homomorphism.

Similarly one defines the Anti-Smarandache semi-near-ring homomorphism:

Definition 7: Let N and N_1 be two Anti-Smarandache semi-near-rings. Then $h: N \rightarrow N_1$ is an *Anti-Smarandache semi-near-ring homomorphism* if h is a homomorphism.

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